

Guidelines for handling research data at the University of Hildesheim Foundation

Preamble

The University of Hildesheim Foundation (SUH) aims to create and preserve knowledge, to give impulses for creative thinking and to make new findings accessible and usable for science and society as well as for future generations. Good research data management reduces the administrative effort for the researchers. The SUH supports its scientists by implementing high quality data management in accordance with ensuring good scientific practice and to promote the transparency of their research. The SUH is committed to a culture of scientific integrity in accordance with the Code of Conduct "Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice"¹ of the German Research Foundation (DFG). These guidelines provide orientation and refer in particular to the "Principles for the Handling of Research Data"² of the Alliance of Science Organisations in Germany and on the DFG "Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data"³.

Research Data

Research data is data created in the course of scientific activity, e. g. through observations, experiments, simulations, surveys, interviews, the study of sources, records, digitisation, or evaluations⁴. They are both the basis and the result of scientific work. Responsible handling of the research data and the software that generates it serves the goal of traceability and verifiability of the research and enables the reuse of the research data and the research software if necessary.

Responsibility and Data Access

The scientists of the SUH are responsible for deciding which digital and non-digital research data are worth archiving and publishing, as well as for the documentation, provision and long-term safeguarding of the research data. Through storing and archiving in a recognized repository⁵, the researchers have fulfilled their obligation to

¹ DFG Code of Conduct Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice (Code of Conduct, 2019). https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/rechtliche_rahmenbedingungen/gute_wissenschaftliche_praxis/kodex_gwp_en.pdf

² Alliance of Science Organisations in Germany, Principles for the Handling of Research Data (2010), https://www.mpg.de/230783/Principles_Research_Data_2010.pdf

³ DFG Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data (2019), https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/proposal_review_decision/applicants/research_data/index.html

⁴ See definition of Rfill - Performance through Diversity (2016), <http://www.rfii.de/?p=2075>

⁵ A repository (archiving system) can be subject-specific or institutional and is recognized in the sense of the FAIR Data Principles.

adhere to good scientific practice (archiving for at least 10 years). In research data management, the scientists observe compliance with ethical, data protection, copyright and confidentiality issues. It is recommended that research data / research software and scientific publications are made publicly accessible in accordance with the Open Access guidelines of the University of Hildesheim Foundation⁶. For this, the choice of an open license (e.g. Creative Commons) is advised for easy reuse. This takes into account the requirements of the research funders and partners. The FAIR Data Principles⁷ as well as software and data citation principles (Data Citation Principles⁸) are being followed. In order to secure the scientific results, the University of Hildesheim Foundation approves planning the handling of research data as early as the proposition of an application and drawing up a research data management plan for this at an early stage. A data management plan documents the collection, processing and storage of research data from data collection, the methods used and workflows to publication.

⁶ Leitlinien der Stiftung Universität Hildesheim zum Open Access-Publizieren, <https://www.uni-hildesheim.de/bibliothek/forschen-publizieren/open-access/leitlinien-der-universitaet-hildesheim/text/> (German language)

⁷ The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁸ Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. Martone M. (ed.) San Diego CA: FORCE11; 2014, <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egy>